

Simulations of Counterflow Dual-Fuel Flames and Implications for DCMC

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Abstract

A Doubly-Conditional Moment Closure (DCMC) solver was presented and used to provide structures of non-premixed counterflow flames of gaseous heptane against methane/air mixtures as the oxidizer in anticipation of future multi-dimensional turbulent combustion calculations of dual-fuel systems. To supplement these calculations and to understand better the structure of such flames, the same counterflow flames were simulated with Cantera. Two methane/air equivalence ratios were considered, one below and one above the lean flammability limit of the methane/air premixed mixture. The effect of flame straining was also investigated by employing two strain rates: one far away from and one close to the critical extinction strain rate. The accuracy of the usual assumption of unity Lewis number employed by the DCMC solver was examined using the Cantera simulations and it was concluded that some discrepancies exist in intermediate species and temperature profiles compared to the case when differential diffusion was taken into account. These differences were enhanced by increased straining. The $Le=1$ model resulted in lower gradients of some species, which in turn resulted in lower scalar dissipation of the mixture fraction and progress variable. The heat release rate profile of the flames implied the existence of two separate reaction zones, which merged at high strain rates. The DCMC model predicted quite accurately the methane/air side of the flame in mixture fraction space, but not to the same degree of accuracy the heptane side of the flame. Moreover, it extended the methane consumption layer and as the strain rate of the flame increased it overpredicted the maximum flame temperature.

Introduction

One of the emerging combustion technologies, with a wide range of applications [1-3], whose development is driven by the current need of reduction of emissions, is the use of dual-fuel combustion systems in different contexts. Therefore, a model that is capable of capturing the turbulence-chemistry interactions at all scales and for all modes of combustion with a wide range of validity and consequently taking into account finite-rate chemistry effects is required to model the behavior of these systems.

One of the methods that have been proposed to satisfy this requirement is Conditional Moment Closure (CMC) method for turbulent reacting flows [4]. This method solves the transport equations of the conditional averages of enthalpy and species mass fractions based on a sample space parameter (mixture fraction for non-premixed flames or reaction progress variable for premixed flames). CMC takes into account detailed chemistry and the main transport phenomena involved in combustion [5]. Importantly, it can also be coupled with Large Eddy Simulation (LES) to produce CMC-LES. CMC-LES has been validated and employed for a wide range of combustion problems such as ignition [6], gaseous flame structure [7], and flames (premixed or non-premixed) close to blow-off [8].

In all the aforementioned cases, a single parameter is enough to capture the physics of the thermochemical system under study, but this is not the case for important dual-fuel flames in

which the two fuels are chemically completely different in nature. In these cases, an increased number of conditioning parameters is required to account for the greater number of degrees of freedom of the thermochemical system. Considering all the above, Doubly Conditional Moment Closure (DCMC) models have been developed but mainly only been applied at the level of fundamental feasibility studies [9-11]. A successful practical simulation model has been developed by Sitte and Mastorakos [12–14] for the simulation of spray jet dual-fuel flames with the choice of a mixture fraction and a reaction progress variable as the two conditioning parameters. Their study has shown that DCMC can capture multi-modal combustion characteristics satisfying one of the most important original requirements and hence that DCMC has a very high potential of proving itself as an essential design tool of future, low-emissions, dual-fuel, fuel-flexible combustors.

This paper has two main objectives: Firstly, to explore a canonical dual-fuel combustion problem using the DCMC solver in a simplified form to examine the basics of this model, and in particular, the dual-fuel non-premixed counterflow flame of heptane (C_7H_{16}) versus a methane (CH_4)/air premixed mixture. The swirling dual-fuel C_7H_{16} - CH_4 /air flame experiment, conducted previously by Sidey and Mastorakos [15] forms the basis of the investigation. Secondly, to analyze the structure of such non-premixed counterflow flames at low and high strain rates to provide insights into the combustion process of dual-fuel systems.

Method

I. CMC and DCMC

In CMC the conditional average with respect to the conditioning parameter ξ of the reactive scalar ϕ is defined as:

$$Q_\phi(\eta) = \langle \phi(\vec{x}, t) |_{\xi(\vec{x}, t) = \eta} \rangle \quad (1)$$

where \vec{x} is the position vector, t is the time, η is the corresponding sample space variable to the conditioning parameter ξ . Here, ξ is the mixture fraction. DCMC can be employed by extending the CMC concept with the introduction of a second conditioning parameter (here, the reaction progress variable, c) with corresponding sample space variable ζ in order to capture the more complex physics of the combustion problem to be solved [4].

$$Q_\phi(\eta, \zeta) = \langle \phi(\vec{x}, t) |_{\xi(\vec{x}, t) = \eta, c(\vec{x}, t) = \zeta} \rangle \quad (2)$$

The mixture fraction takes the value of unity ($\xi = 1$) at the locations where pure C_7H_{16} is found and the value of zero ($\xi = 0$) when only a pure CH_4 /air premixed mixture of a fixed equivalence ratio is present. The reaction progress variable is defined such that it takes the value of unity ($c = 1$) when locally chemical equilibrium has been achieved and the value of zero ($c = 0$) if no reaction has taken place. It can be defined based on a linear combination of species mass fractions Y_ψ [12] which are functions of the local mixture fraction:

$$c(\xi) = \frac{Y_\psi^0(\xi) - Y_\psi(\xi)}{Y_\psi^0(\xi) - Y_\psi^{eq}(\xi)} \quad (3)$$

where the superscripts “0” and “eq” denote the mixing line and the equilibrium state respectively. In DCMC, and in Cantera [16], this linear combination was defined to be the sum of the mass fractions of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and water so that the reaction progress variable increases monotonically and takes values only in the range between 0 and 1:

$$Y_\psi = Y_{CO_2} + Y_{CO} + Y_{H_2O} \quad (4)$$

II. 0D-DCMC

“0D-DCMC” is the solution of DCMC under the special conditions of spatial homogeneity and with prescribed scalar dissipation rate distributions in the mixture fraction-reaction progress variable space. The solutions serve as reference and offer insights into the process. The 0D-DCMC equations for the conditional averages of the reactive scalar (species mass fraction) ϕ and enthalpy h can be found in [14] and are:

$$\frac{\partial Q_\phi}{\partial t} = \langle N_\xi | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_\phi}{\partial \eta^2} + 2 \langle N_{\xi c} | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_\phi}{\partial \eta \partial \zeta} + \langle N_c | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_\phi}{\partial \zeta^2} + \langle \dot{\omega}_\phi | \eta, \zeta \rangle - \langle \omega_c^* | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial Q_\phi}{\partial \zeta} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_h}{\partial t} = \langle N_\xi | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_h}{\partial \eta^2} + 2 \langle N_{\xi c} | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_h}{\partial \eta \partial \zeta} + \langle N_c | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_h}{\partial \zeta^2} - \langle \omega_c^* | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial Q_h}{\partial \zeta} \quad (6)$$

where $\langle \omega_c^* | \eta, \zeta \rangle$ is the conditional apparent reaction rate given by:

$$\langle \omega_c^* | \eta, \zeta \rangle = \frac{1}{\partial Q_\psi / \partial \zeta} (\langle \dot{\omega}_\psi | \eta, \zeta \rangle + \langle N_\xi | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_\psi}{\partial \eta^2} + 2 \langle N_{\xi c} | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_\psi}{\partial \eta \partial \zeta} + \langle N_c | \eta, \zeta \rangle \frac{\partial^2 Q_\psi}{\partial \zeta^2}) \quad (7)$$

In Eqs (5), (6) and (7), $\dot{\omega}_\phi$ is the production rate of the reactive scalar ϕ , N_ξ and N_c denote the scalar dissipation rates of mixture fraction and reaction progress variable respectively and $N_{\xi c}$ is the cross-scalar dissipation rate of those two quantities. The scalar dissipation rates are defined by the following three equations in which D is the diffusion coefficient:

$$N_\xi = D \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \right)^2, \quad N_c = D \left(\frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \right)^2, \quad N_{\xi c} = D \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \quad (8)$$

Note that the above formulation assumes that the Lewis number (Le) takes the value of unity. The conditional average of the production rate of the reactive scalar ϕ was modelled using the primary closure hypothesis assuming that the fluctuations are small [12]. The conditional average of the scalar dissipation rate of the mixture fraction was modelled using the amplitude mapping closure (AMC) bell-shaped curve [14]

$$\langle N_\xi | \eta, \zeta \rangle = N_{\xi_{max}} G(\eta) \quad (9)$$

where,

$$G(\eta) = \exp(-2[erf^{-1}(2\eta - 1)]^2) \quad (10)$$

It was assumed that the cross-scalar dissipation rate was zero:

$$\langle N_{\xi c} | \eta, \zeta \rangle = 0 \quad (11)$$

For the profile of the conditional average of the scalar dissipation rate of the reaction progress variable as a function of the sampling variables η and ζ a profile obtained from the Cantera simulation of premixed counterflow flames of the resulting mixture from the combination of

fuel and oxidizer quantities of mass η and $1 - \eta$ respectively of the counterflow premixed flame under study against the equilibrium products of that mixture was employed:

$$\langle N_c |_{\eta, \zeta} \rangle = N_c^{\blacksquare}(\eta, \zeta), \quad (12)$$

where “ \blacksquare ” denotes the unscaled profile produced by Cantera. Note that for the cases for which a premixed flame did not exist, a value of zero was assumed for the scalar dissipation rate of the reaction progress variable for all reaction progress variable values. Eqs (5), (6) and (7) were solved using the CLIO code [17-18] which was developed for the solution of CMC related partial differential equations. The simulations were initialized by assuming a progress towards the full combustion of the reactants (i.e. full conversion to CO_2 and H_2O , without the formation of intermediate species) profile over the $\eta - \zeta$ space for all conditional quantities and giving priority to the combustion of CH_4 over C_7H_{16} . The boundary conditions at $\eta = 0$ and $\eta = 1$ were set as the initial conditions in reference [15] while at $\zeta = 0$ and $\zeta = 1$ mixing line and equilibrium conditions were enforced respectively. Pressure was assumed to be atmospheric, the inlet temperature of C_7H_{16} was set equal to the boiling temperature of heptane ($T_{C_7H_{16}} = 371.5 K$) [19] and the inlet temperature of the CH_4 /air premixed mixture with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$ or $\phi_{pmx} = 0.56$ was set equal to $T_{CH_4/air} = 300 K$. For the maxima of the scalar dissipation rates used in the simulations see Table 1.

III. Cantera Simulations

Counterflow flames using exactly the same initial conditions for the C_7H_{16} (fuel) stream and the CH_4 /air premixed mixture (oxidizer) stream as in the 0D-DCMC simulation of the C_7H_{16} - CH_4 /air dual-fuel counterflow flame were solved using Cantera using both a unity Lewis number transport model and a mixture averaged transport model. The higher equivalence ratio of $\phi_{pmx} = 0.56$ was also considered, to provide insight into canonical flame structures seen in the turbulent swirl flame experiments of Sidey and Mastorakos [15]. The detailed mechanism created by Smallbone et al. [20] was employed and tested for laminar flame speeds of freely propagating flames of CH_4 and C_7H_{16} and for the extinction strain rates of C_7H_{16} non-premixed flames with comparison with experimental results [21-24]. Fig. 1 depicts the predicted and experimentally measured values of laminar flame speed (S_L) for a range of equivalence ratio values at STP conditions for both C_7H_{16} (Sileghem et al. experimental data [22]) and CH_4 (Whang et al. experimental data [24]):

Figure 1. Laminar flame speed of C_7H_{16} /air and CH_4 /air premixed mixtures of various equivalence ratios at STP conditions as predicted by the chosen mechanism compared to experimental data found in the literature.

It is evident that experimental data and the predictions of the simulations using this detailed mechanism are similar with the degree of agreement increasing as the equivalence ratio increases for both C_7H_{16} and CH_4 . Concerning the extinction strain rate of non-premixed flames, nitrogen-diluted C_7H_{16} diffusion flames at various mass fractions $Y_{C_7H_{16},f}$ at a temperature of $T_f = 533 K$ against a pure air oxidizer stream of temperature $T_{ox} = 533 K$ were measured [21]. The extinction strain rate was defined as

$$k_{ext,ox} = \frac{2V_{ox}}{w} \left(1 + \frac{V_f \sqrt{\rho_f}}{V_{ox} \sqrt{\rho_{ox}}} \right) \quad (13)$$

where V_f, ρ_f and V_{ox}, ρ_{ox} are the [normal] velocities to the flame plane and the densities of the fuel and oxidizer streams respectively, and w is the distance between the nozzles. In the simulations, the momenta of the two streams were set equal so that the flame would be positioned in the centre of the simulation domain while a nozzle distance of $w = 0.01 m$ was chosen. The global strain rates (a) of those counterflow flames was defined by

$$a = \frac{V_f + V_{ox}}{w} \quad (14)$$

and the resulting scalar dissipation rate (needed for one-to-one comparison between DCMC that solves in mixture fraction space and Cantera that solves in real space) was determined by Eq. (15):

$$a = \pi N_{\xi_{max}} \quad (15)$$

Table 1 includes the strain rate values computed using Eq. (15) for the simulations.

Table 1. Maximum scalar dissipation rate values ($N_{\xi_{max}}$ and $N_{c_{max}}$) and global strain rate (a) of the flames simulated using 0D-DCMC and Cantera.

Simulation [φ_{pmx}, No]	$N_{\xi_{max}} (s^{-1})$	$a (s^{-1})$	$N_{c_{max}}^{\square} (s^{-1})$
0.14, 1	32.94	103.48	1598.13
0.14, 2	98.82	310.44	
0.56, 1	49.70	156.13	1480.76
0.56, 2	129.21	405.93	

The heptane non-premixed flame extinction strain rates from the measurement [21] and the simulations are shown in Fig. 2. The good agreement, together with the good agreement of the predicted laminar flame speed of both fuels, suggest that this detailed mechanism should be sufficient for the dual-fuel problem under investigation.

Figure 2. Local at oxidizer side extinction strain rate of a counterflow non-premixed flame with air at $T_{ox} = 533 K$ as the oxidizer and nitrogen diluted mixtures of C_7H_{16} as the fuel versus C_7H_{16} mass fraction in the fuel stream $Y_{C_7H_{16},f}$ as predicted by the chosen mechanism and as reported by Reference [21].

Results and Discussion

I. Flame structure for two CH_4 /air equivalence (ϕ_{pmx}) ratios

Counterflow non-premixed flames with pure air ($\phi_{pmx} = 0$) as oxidizer with exactly the same temperature and pressure conditions as the flame under study in this paper extinguished at a global strain rate of $a \approx 279 s^{-1}$. Under the same conditions, counterflow non-premixed flames whose oxidizer stream was a CH_4 /air premixed mixture of $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$, $\phi_{pmx} = 0.47$, (below the CH_4 /air lean flammability limit of $\phi_{LFL} = 0.5$ [25]), and $\phi_{pmx} = 0.56$ (above the CH_4 /air lean flammability limit) extinguished approximately at $a \approx 330 s^{-1}$, $a \approx 425 s^{-1}$ and $a \approx 415 s^{-1}$ respectively. The addition of CH_4 in the oxidizer stream initially causes a slight increase in the extinction strain rate as the CH_4 /air lean flammability limit is approached and then causes a decrease. The manifestation of a maximum can be attributed to the competition of the two fuels (CH_4 and C_7H_{16}) for the consumption of oxygen.

The structure of flames of the two equivalence ratios under consideration with $a = 310 s^{-1}$ can be seen in Figs 3-4. The profiles of the volumetric Heat Release Rate (HRR) of the two counterflow C_7H_{16} - CH_4 /air flames under consideration (Fig. 3, left graph) have two maxima whose region corresponds to the oxidation of CH_4 (right maximum) and C_7H_{16} (left maximum). At a higher ϕ_{pmx} , the maximum value of the CH_4 oxidation region increases while the maximum of the C_7H_{16} oxidation region decreases.

Fig. 3, right graph, shows the temperature (T) profile of the flame for the two values of the equivalence ratio under study. It is evident from this graph that as ϕ_{pmx} increases the temperature increases everywhere across the flame. The greatest increase occurs to the right of the temperature profile maximum which is displaced towards the CH_4 /air side in accordance with the change observed in the HRR profile. The C_7H_{16} , CH_4 , O_2 and C_2H_4 mass fraction distributions are presented in Fig. 4, left graph. On the C_7H_{16} side, C_2H_4 forms a peak at the location where CH_4 is present, which is also the location where the HRR profile takes negative values. This is expected as on the heptane side endothermic pyrolysis of the heptane takes place producing these smaller hydrocarbons.

Fig. 4, right graph, shows the profile of formaldehyde, hydroxide and hydroperoxyl. At the low ϕ_{pmx} , CH_2O (which is formed in two regions, one in each side) is mainly formed in the

C_7H_{16} side, while at a greater ϕ_{pmx} the same substance is mainly formed at the CH_4 /air side because of the significantly enhanced combustion of CH_4 at this equivalence ratio above the lean flammability limit of CH_4 /air premixed mixture. OH is mainly formed in the region where temperature takes its highest values with both the location and the value of the maximum of its mass fraction profile following the behaviour of the temperature profile. In the case in which the equivalence ratio is greater than the CH_4 /air lean flammability limit, and hence when CH_4 is combusted in premixed mode, the thickness of the OH bell-shaped curve increases significantly increasing the distance between the two CH_2O regions. HO_2 radicals participate in termination steps, but they are also involved in the production of radicals at high temperatures [26]. At a higher ϕ_{pmx} the region of their main presence is displaced towards the CH_4 /air side and their mass fraction there increases but their “leakage” decreases.

Figure 3. HRR (left graph) and temperature (right graph) profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a strain rate of $a = 310 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the two equivalence ratios under consideration.

Figure 4. O_2 , C_7H_{16} , CH_4 and C_2H_4 (left graph) and OH , CH_2O and HO_2 (right graph) mass fraction profiles and of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a strain rate of $a = 310 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the two equivalence ratios under consideration.

II. Flame structure at two strain rates for a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of 0.14

Figs 5, and 6 show the profiles of the same quantities as Figs 3, and 4 respectively. In these figures the counterflow non-premixed flames of the C_7H_{16} - CH_4 /air dual-fuel system under investigation have $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$ but a different global strain rate value. As noted in the beginning of the “Results and Discussion” section, the extinction strain rate of the C_7H_{16} -

CH_4 /air flame system for this equivalence ratio is $a \approx 330 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The two strain rates chosen were $a \approx 103 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (away from extinction) and $a \approx 310 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (close to extinction).

Figure 5. HRR (left graph) and temperature (right graph) profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

Figure 6. O_2 , C_7H_{16} , CH_4 and C_2H_4 (left graph) and OH , CH_2O and HO_2 (right graph) mass fraction profiles in the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

As the strain rate increases and approaches the value of the extinction strain rate, the C_7H_{16} oxidation is significantly enhanced, indicated by the more pronounced maximum in the C_7H_{16} side of the HRR profile (Fig. 5, left graph), while the flame becomes thinner since the two maxima tend to merge because of the greater straining of the flame. The temperature (Fig. 5, right graph) decreases as expected since the increase in the strain rate decreases the residence time, and the maximum moves towards the C_7H_{16} side. Straining the flame reduces the mass fractions of CH_4 and C_2H_4 on that side (Fig. 6, left graph) and causes the manifestation of O_2 “leakage” in the reaction zone (Fig. 6, left graph). As the strain rate increases, the peak CH_2O and HO_2 mass fraction values increase and the OH mass fraction decreases, consistent with incomplete combustion as residence time decreases and extinction is approached.

III. Effect of the transport model

The main aim of this section is to examine the effect of the transport model on the flame structure predicted by the Cantera laminar flame simulation. The 0D-DCMC model uses a unity Lewis number transport model. It is thus useful to assess the error introduced in the

predictions using this assumption. Note that in Figs 7-11 the stoichiometric mixture fraction (ξ_{st}) location is marked with the ‘dashdot’ vertical black line.

Figure 7. HRR and temperature profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

Figure 8. CH_2O and OH mass fraction profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

Figure 9. CH_4 , C_7H_{16} , and O_2 mass fraction profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

Figure 10. Y_p profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio $\phi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

The normalized distributions of HRR and temperature and the mass fractions profiles in mixture fraction space agree with their distribution in physical space. It is apparent from Fig. 7 that the maxima of temperature and HRR coincide in mixture fraction space at a mixture fraction value very close to the stoichiometric mixture fraction. CH_2O (Fig. 8) is mainly produced in the C_7H_{16} side while OH is effectively produced in the CH_4 /air side (Fig. 8). CH_2O forms two local maxima, one on the C_7H_{16} side and the other in the CH_4 /air side relatively close to the location of the maximum flame temperature, as is the case for the local maximum in the OH distribution in the CH_4 /air side. O_2 and CH_4 are mainly consumed in the vicinity of the stoichiometric mixture fraction (Fig. 9). The quantity Y_p was chosen to be shown because it is used in the calculation of the reaction progress variable, which as noted above, is the second conditioning parameter of the 0D-DCMC model.

For both strain rates, a temperature underprediction is observed in the C_7H_{16} side (here the region where $\xi > \xi_{st}$), but the location of the maximum remains the same (Fig. 7). The value of that maximum is overpredicted at high strain rates (Fig. 7, right graph). The unity Lewis number transport model overpredicts the absolute values of the local extrema of the HRR profile, a distortion that is amplified at higher strain rates (Fig 7, right graph) and underpredicts the modulus of the HRR in the negative region away from the local minimum. There is a significant underprediction of CH_2O mass fraction in the C_7H_{16} side, a discrepancy which is also enhanced with increasing the strain rate (Fig 8, right graph), and a similar overprediction of that quantity in the CH_4 /air side (here the region where $\xi < \xi_{st}$, see Fig. 8). The same happens for OH mass fraction on that side and again the straining of the flame enhances the differences in the predictions between the two transport models. The location of the local maxima of the last two quantities in the CH_4 /air side have been slightly displaced towards the stoichiometric mixture fraction value.

The C_7H_{16} mass fraction (Fig. 9) is well predicted over the range mixture fraction values that it has a non-negligible value for both strain rates. The predicted curve of the mass fraction of CH_4 from the unity Lewis number transport model suffers the opposite distortions compared to CH_2O in terms of modulus, which is expected as CH_2O appears in the chain branching reaction of CH_4 and given that the C_7H_{16} distribution has not been seriously affected by the use of the unity Lewis number transport model. O_2 mass fraction is underpredicted at the greater strain rate (Fig. 9, right). The maximum of the profile of Y_p at the lower strain rate (Fig. 10, left graph) is well predicted by the unity Lewis transport model with a slight overprediction of the maximum of that curve. Increasing the strain rate of the flame (Fig. 10, right graph) causes a

greater overprediction of the global maximum of the curve of Y_{ψ} distribution in the mixture fraction space.

Fig. 11 depicts the mixture fraction, reaction progress variable and cross- scalar dissipation rate profiles for $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$ computed using the two transport models. The effect of the change in each profile of the transport model employed is the same for both strain rates. The most significant and evident change is the decrease of the values of the scalar dissipation rates. The general trends remain the same.

Figure 11. Scalar dissipation profiles of the counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$ for the two global strain rates under consideration.

IV. 0D-DCMC results

Figs 12 – 13 depict the temperature and C_7H_{16} , O_2 , CH_4 , CH_2O and OH distributions in the $\eta - \zeta$ space as predicted by the 0D-DCMC solver for two of the cases under consideration (for the two equivalence ratios at their higher respective strain rate values) . The green dashed line denotes the stoichiometric composition while the blue dashed line in the graphs of those figures is the $c = fn(\xi)$ curve of the 1D counterflow non-premixed flame under the same conditions. Only the values of plotted quantities along the last curve in the $\eta - \zeta$ space have a physical meaning for that flame studied in Cantera in the previous sub-sections, although in principle all possible states of the problem can be found on these diagrams.

Figure 12. T and C_7H_{16} and O_2 mass fraction distributions in the $\eta - \zeta$ space as predicted by the 0D-DCMC solver for counterflow non-premixed flames with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 98.82/s$ and $N_{c_{max}} = 1598.13/s$ (left graphs) and a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.56$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 129.21/s$ and $N_{c_{max}} = 1481.76/s$ (right graphs).

Figure 13. CH_4 , CH_2O and OH mass fraction distributions in the $\eta - \zeta$ space as predicted by the 0D-DCMC model for counterflow non-premixed flames with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 98.82/s$ and $N_{c_{max}}^{\blacksquare} = 1598.13/s$ (left graphs) and a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.56$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 129.21/s$ and $N_{c_{max}}^{\blacksquare} = 1481.76/s$ (right graphs).

It is evident in the first right graph of Fig. 12 from the temperature variation along the ζ axis that the CH_4 /air mixture of higher equivalence ratio is combustible contrary to the case where the same equivalence ratio is below the lean flammability limit of that mixture (Fig. 12, left first graph). Higher temperatures are reached in the second case (Fig. 12, right first graph). At a higher CH_4 /air equivalence ratio more C_7H_{16} is consumed at higher ζ values for all possible η (Fig. 12, right second graph) as is the case for O_2 (Fig. 12, right third graph) since its presence region in the $\eta - \zeta$ space is contracted. Fig. 13 indicates that the CH_4 mass fraction is significantly lower at the higher ζ values region at all η values when the CH_4 /air equivalence

ratio is above the lean flammability limit of the CH_4 /air mixture (Fig. 13, right first graph) in agreement with the fact that when this is the case the CH_4 is being burnt in an enhanced, premixed mode. The CH_2O production region in the $\eta - \zeta$ space is smaller, touches the ζ axis and has a smaller in value maximum displaced at a greater η value and smaller ζ value in the higher CH_4 /air equivalence ratio case (Fig. 13, right second graph) in accordance with what has been stated above. Finally, the OH production region even though in both cases is positioned in the high temperature region at the lower CH_4 /air equivalence ratio extents over a smaller ζ range (Fig. 13 left third graph) since the high temperature region in this case also exhibits the same relative behaviour compared to the higher CH_4 /air equivalence ratio case.

Figures 14-17 depict the 0D-DCMC results of the simulation of the dual-fuel counterflow $C_7H_{16} - CH_4$ /air flame for the conditions stated in Table 1 along the $c = fn(\xi)$ curve in the $\eta - \zeta$ 0D-DCMC plane corresponding to the flame being modelled compared with the Cantera predictions employing a unity Lewis number transport model (since this is the transport model the 0D-DCMC model uses). In almost all cases the temperature (right graph) is overpredicted by the 0D-DCMC model in the C_7H_{16} side of the stoichiometric mixture fraction region, but then slightly underpredicted as a value of unity mixture fraction is being approached. This is not the case for the flame with $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.56$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 129.21/s$ and $N_c^{\square}_{max} = 1480.76/s$ for which the temperature is overpredicted in the whole C_7H_{16} side of the flame, but once more with a decreasing degree as the composition of pure C_7H_{16} is being approached. For all the flames the temperature in the CH_4 /air side are accurately predicted as is the case for the C_7H_{16} mass fraction profile (left graphs). The general trend of OH mass fraction distribution (left graphs) is captured by the 0D-DCMC model even though the maximum is overpredicted to an extent increasing with the strain rate in agreement with the prediction trend of the global maximum of the temperature profile (right graph) and even though the width of the bell-shaped part of the distribution is greater. The disagreement again is manifested essentially in the C_7H_{16} side of the stoichiometric mixture fraction region. For the lower CH_4 /air equivalence ratio value the CH_4 mass fraction is underpredicted in the C_7H_{16} side of the flame with its local maximum being displaced away from the stoichiometric mixture fraction value in agreement with the predictions of the model for the OH mass fraction distribution. At the higher CH_4 /air equivalence ratio the CH_4 mass fraction local maximum is overpredicted so that at higher mixture fraction values than the one corresponding to that maximum the CH_4 mass fraction value continues to be overpredicted.

Figure 14. CH_4 , C_7H_{16} , OH and T distributions along the $c = fn(\xi)$ flame curve as predicted by the 0D-DCMC model for counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 32.94/s$ and $N_c^{\square}_{max} = 1598.13/s$.

Figure 15. CH_4 , C_7H_{16} , OH and T distributions along the $c = fn(\xi)$ flame curve as predicted by the 0D-DCMC model for counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.14$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 98.82/s$ and $N_c^{\square}_{max} = 1598.13/s$.

Figure 16. CH_4 , C_7H_{16} , OH and T distributions along the $c = fn(\xi)$ flame curve as predicted by the 0D-DCMC model for counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.56$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 49.70/s$ and $N_c^{\square}_{max} = 1480.76/s$.

Figure 17. CH_4 , C_7H_{16} , OH and T distributions along the $c = fn(\xi)$ flame curve as predicted by the 0D-DCMC model for counterflow non-premixed flame with a CH_4 /air equivalence ratio of $\varphi_{pmx} = 0.56$, $N_{\xi_{max}} = 129.21/s$ and $N_c^{\square}_{max} = 1480.76/s$.

Conclusions

Numerical simulations of dual-fuel C_7H_{16} - CH_4 /air counterflow non-premixed flames have been presented with the aim of analysing the structure of such flames both close and away from extinction and with a CH_4 /air mixture below and above its nominal lean flammability limit. These simulations were created using Cantera and a detailed mechanism that was validated as

far as the laminar flame speed and extinction strain rate of C_7H_{16} /air and CH_4 /air mixtures were concerned.

As the φ_{pmx} increased approaching the lean flammability limit the extinction strain rate manifested a maximum. The mass fraction profiles of the flame reflected the dual-fuel nature of the flame and as the flame was strained the C_7H_{16} flame was enhanced.

The use of a unity Lewis number transport model had a non-negligible effect on the prediction of temperature, intermediate species, O_2 and CH_4 mass fraction profiles but not so much on the prediction of the profiles of C_7H_{16} and full combustion products. Generally, the location of consumption or production of CH_4 oxidation related species was displaced towards the CH_4 /air side and the straining of the flame enhanced the degree of manifestation of the discrepancies. The unity Lewis number transport decreased the values of the scalar dissipation rates of the flame in both conditioning parameter dimensions.

Finally, the 0D-DCMC model predicted quite accurately the distribution of species and temperature in the CH_4 /air side of the flame in the mixture fraction space but with some discrepancies in the C_7H_{16} side, particularly close to the stoichiometric mixture fraction value, given that its results were compared with the Cantera predictions for the same flame using the same transport model. The consumption region of CH_4 predicted was extended compared to that predicted by Cantera and the local maximum of the mass fraction profile of CH_4 was overpredicted at high CH_4 /air equivalence ratios but underpredicted at low values of that quantity. As the strain rate of the flame increased the maximum temperature of the flame became increasingly overpredicted.

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